

EPIDEMIOLOGY, CLINICAL ASPECTS AND MODERN METHODS OF THE TREATMENT OF CHRONIC LYMPHOCYTIC LEUKEMIA

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Abstract

Chronic lymphocytic leukemia is the most common type of leukemia in Western Europe and North America. It is mainly a disease of the elderly [9]. Average age of incidence - 72 years [5]. The pathological substrate is cells of the immune system - predominantly mature lymphocytes with a B-phenotype [1]. The clinical picture is variable, the rate of development of the disease is characterized by a wide range both in objective data and in hematological analyzes. The disease can be asymptomatic for many years, and is detected only during routine examination as an incidental finding. In such cases, a strategy of observation and waiting is chosen, without applying specific treatment. The main goals of treatment are to achieve complete or partial remission with improvement and stabilization of the clinical and hematological picture. [10].

To study the features of the epidemiology, clinical course and modern methods of treating CLL, a study was conducted on the basis of a database of 50 patients registered at the Consultative and Diagnostic Center of the Oncological Institute, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova. It was found that the main group with this diagnosis is people 55-75 years old (62%). The mean age of diagnosis among the selected group is 63 years. The incidence of CLL among men (58%) is slightly higher than among women (42%). The use of bio immunotherapy allows you to establish a positive trend in the course of the disease, as well as improve the quality of life of patients [4].

Keywords: chronic lymphocytic leukemia, epidemiology, clinical course, treatment.

Introduction

Chronic lymphocytic leukemia is a malignant lymphoproliferative process characterized by progressive accumulation of lymphoid cells in the peripheral blood, bone marrow, and lymphoid tissue. [6, p.146]. The pathogenetic mechanism is a mutation in the progenitor cell - lymphopoiesis, being malignant, the cell retains the ability to differentiate into an adult cell. The morphological substrate of this process is atypical mature lymphocytes, characterized by functional incompetence. In most cases (95-98%) cells involved in the pathological process are B-cells, in some cases (2-5%) the substrate is represented by T cells. Patients with B-cell form are characterized by the presence of CD19/CD5/CD23/CD20/CD24 - positive immunophenotype [6, p.146]. Approximately 90% of patients have chromosomal mutations, the most common of which is a deletion of the long arm of chromosome 13, that is found in 55% of cases. In 18% of cases, there is a deletion of the long arm of chromosome 11, in 7% of cases, a deletion of the short arm of chromosome 17 is detected, 4% of cases - translocation of chromosome 14. [1, p. 209] CLL ranks second after acute leukemia in the overall incidence of leukemia. It is the most common type of leukemia among Caucasians. More than 70% of patients diagnosed with CLL are in the age group of 50-70 years. On average, it is diagnosed at age 55. CLL is more common in men [2, p.5] In the Republic of Moldova, the overall incidence of CLL is 1.2 cases per 100,000 inhabitants [2, p.5]. In the United States, between 2015 and 2019, the incidence of new

cases of chronic lymphocytic leukemia was 4.7 per 100,000 people per year, the death rate is 1.1 per 100,000 people per year. The prevalence for 2019 is about 200,766 people [3]. The incidence increases by more than 30 out of 100,000 people per year over the age of 80 [5, p.1]. Presence of chromosomal mutations suggests a genetic predisposition to CLL, which increases the risk for family members of patients by 6-9 times. [1-p.210, 6-p.147] CLL includes several stages according to the clinical and hematological classification: the initial stage, the stage of clinical and hematological manifestations and the terminal stage [8, p.158]. Stadiation of the disease has been proposed in systems K. Rai (1975) и J. Binet (1981), that take into account the presence of clinical signs, objective examination data peripheral lymph nodes, hepatosplenomegaly), instrumental studies, laboratory changes [5,2-p.14, 8, p.161]

Aim of the study

Study of the epidemiology, clinical aspects, laboratory changes and modern methods of treatment of chronic lymphocytic leukemia.

Materials and methods

The study included 50 patients diagnosed with chronic lymphocytic leukemia, registered at the Consultative and Diagnostic Center of the Oncological Institute from 2015 to 2022. A retrospective method of statistical research was used. To fill in statistical questionnaires, data from medical records of patients observed in the outpatient clinic were used: gender, age of patients, clinical signs and examination data, laboratory

tests, bone marrow aspirates, treatment methods depending on the stage, as well as the results of immunohistochemical and immunophenotypic studies.

Results

The age of patients included in the study ranged from 38 to 88 years. The mean age of the patients was

63.88 years. The largest group consisted of patients of the age group 65-74 (16-32%) and 55-64 (15-30%). Least of all, CLL was diagnosed in groups over 84 (1-2%) and under 45 years (1-2%). (Pic.1).

Pic. 1 Distribution of patients with CLL depending on age

In the distribution depending on sex, with a slight advantage, the highest incidence is observed in men (29 - 58%). (Pic.2)

Pic. 2 Distribution of patients by gender

As for the social aspect of this disease, since the main percentage of morbidity occurs in groups of 55-64 (30%) and 65-74 (32%) years, most patients are people of retirement and pre-retirement age. In total, out of

50 people in the observed group, 27 (54%) are pensioners, 7 (14%) are persons with disabilities, and another 7 (14%) patients are employed and able-bodied population

Pic. 3 Distribution of patients depending on the phase of the disease

At the time of diagnosis, 31 patients (62%) were in the initial phase of the disease. The initial phase of the disease is characterized by the absence of clinical manifestations (90.3%) and is most often detected during routine laboratory tests (leukocytosis $< 30.0 \cdot 10^9/l$ and lymphocytosis in peripheral blood). In some patients in the initial phase of the disease, non-specific clinical manifestations (9.6%) were observed: general weakness, asthenia, subfebrile condition or weight loss.

In the stage of clinical and hematological manifestations, CLL was diagnosed in 18 patients (36%). This phase of the disease is characterized by the appearance

of clinical signs such as: general weakness (86%), lymphadenopathy (58%), anemic syndrome (14%), hepatosplenomegaly (46%), weight loss (10%), general pain (18%), headache (14%), fever (10%). In 6% of cases, an asymptomatic course of the disease was observed for the patient. (Pic.4)

In the general blood test, leukocytosis is observed (max. value $393 \cdot 10^9/l$), and lymphocytosis with an increase of up to 80-90% in peripheral blood.

The terminal phase of the disease (2%) is characterized by somatic decompensation: weight loss, fever, progression of anemia, marked enlargement of the lymph node, liver and spleen.

Pic. 4 The main complaints of patients in the phase of clinical and hematological manifestations.

As CLL progressed, patients developed autoimmune complications (8%), anemia (16%), and infectious diseases (12%).

Immunophenotyping methods were used to diagnose CLL in some patients (32%) in order to detect diagnostic markers CD10, CD5, CD19, CD23, CD20.

In 28% of patients, a bone marrow puncture was performed as a diagnostic method with the detection of lymphocytes over 30%, in 16% of cases a puncture of peripheral lymph nodes was performed.

CLL was treated both on an outpatient basis (46%) and in a hospital setting (16%), 38% of patients did not need specific treatment. When Rituximab was used in monotherapy, as well as in R-CHOP, R-COP regimens, complete remission was observed in 67% of cases, and partial remission in 33% of cases. When using schemes with the use of chimeric monoclonal antibodies, positive dynamics in the clinical picture was noticed, a decrease in tumor formations, the absence of significant lymphadenopathy during physical examination, a significant decrease in the level of lymphocytosis and leukocytosis in the peripheral blood.

In cases of autoimmune manifestations, especially hemolytic anemia and autoimmune thrombocytopenia, glucocorticoids (dexamethasone, prednisolone) were used in 9.6% of cases.

RBC transfusion was used as replacement therapy for hemoglobin levels < 7.0-8.0 g/dL in 3.2% of cases.

Discussion

Chronic lymphocytic leukemia is an incurable disease. Despite how far modern treatments have come, CLL therapy aims to improve the patient's symptoms and quality of life. The main age group with these diagnoses is people 55-75 years old (62%), with an average age of diagnosis of 63.8 years. With a slight advantage, the incidence rate among men (58%) is higher than among women (42%). Most patients were diagnosed with CLL at the initial stage of the disease 62% - 90.3% of which were asymptomatic. In the phase of clinical manifestations (36%), the dominant symptom is general weakness 86% and peripheral lymphadenopathy 58%. In the initial stage of the disease, with an asymptomatic course in stages 0, I-II Rai or A and B Binet, specific treatment is not carried out, clinical and hematological control is prescribed (watch and wait tactics) every 3 months. The use of regimens with Rituximab allows to achieve positive dynamics and establish clinical and hematological remission.

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